

CARDIAC ISCHEMIA

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6567762>

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Abstract: Ischemic heart disease, or ischemic heart disease, is a chronic or acute disorder of the blood supply to the myocardium (the layer of muscle in the heart). This is because the heart does not get enough oxygen. This occurs when arterial blood is given to the heart muscle in limited amounts due to coronary artery injury.

The acute form of ischemic heart disease is myocardial infarction, the chronic form is angina.

In many developed countries, cardiovascular disease is at the top of the sad list of causes of death. In recent years, there has been a declining trend in this cause. Since 2015, the death rate from cardiovascular disease has accounted for less than half of all deaths and continues to decline.

However, this figure is still higher than in European countries. Although diseases of the circulatory system are the leading cause of death in all developed countries of the world, the mortality rate from cardiovascular diseases in the European Union is significantly lower than in Russia, in Europe in 2015 the figure was 36.7%.

Diseases of the circulatory system include ischemic heart disease, which causes more than half of all cardiovascular deaths. According to statistics, in 2018, ischemia of the heart caused 53% of deaths due to diseases of the circulatory system - this is 24% of the total number of deaths (3% of deaths were caused by myocardial infarction).

Causes of ischemic heart disease

The most common cause of narrowing of blood vessels is the formation of atherosclerotic plaques on the walls of blood vessels due to the accumulation of fat. Therefore, the risk group includes people who have many conditions for the accumulation of cholesterol in the blood vessels: smokers, alcohol abusers, people with diabetes and obesity, people with a genetic predisposition to hyperlipidemia.

Symptoms of coronary heart disease

The first symptoms of ischemic heart disease:

Shortness of breath. This can happen during a brisk walk or climb stairs, as well as during quiet activities.

Arrhythmia. Interruptions in heart function, rapid heartbeat.

Hypertension. Sudden jumps in blood pressure.

Pressure angina. Pressure pain in the back of the chest, neck and left shoulder.

Myocardial infarction. It is similar to angina pectoris but is not controlled by medication. It is accompanied by severe pain in the heart. Indicates the development of cardiovascular disease. It is considered life-threatening due to spontaneous heart muscle damage.

Ischemia can also occur in people who do not have specific factors for the development of cardiovascular disease. It is therefore important to know about the symptoms of coronary artery disease. The sooner a circulatory disorder is detected, the better the chances of successful treatment.

However, the development of coronary heart disease is often slow and almost asymptomatic in the early stages (rarely does a person notice pain in the heart area and shortness of breath). At the initial stage, it is necessary to undergo regular preventive examinations by a cardiologist and therapist to diagnose the disease.

There are currently several ways to treat coronary heart disease. Usually, the doctor prescribes not one, but a set of therapeutic measures based on the diagnosis.

Prevention of heart disease

Everyone knows that any disease is easier to prevent than to cure. Therefore, preventive measures to maintain vascular and vascular health should not be neglected. First and foremost, a person needs to eliminate the obvious risk factors for cardiovascular disease: quitting smoking, minimizing alcohol consumption, and avoiding fatty foods and foods high in cholesterol. You should also pay attention to physical activity (especially cardio - walking, cycling, dancing, swimming). It not only helps to lose weight, but also strengthens the walls of blood vessels. You should have a blood test every six months to check your blood sugar and cholesterol levels.

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